

DETERMINATION OF THRESHOLDS OF K_p AND LATENCY FOR POST-STORM IONOSPHERIC DEPRESSIONS

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Despite the rapid development of satellite technology and the Internet, ionospheric HF radio propagation remains an important and reliable option for establishing communications over long distances, sometimes on global ones. The ionospheric channel is used as an emergency one for establishing radio communications between civil aviation aircrafts and control centers.

Since the channel is ionospheric, both regular variations of the main characteristics of the ionosphere and sporadically occurring plasma irregularities have an essential impact on its parameters. One of the most significant processes impacting HF propagation is post-storm depressions, leading to a decrease in the electron concentration and critical frequency (foF2) after geomagnetic storms. At the present time, space weather centers operate for the needs of civil aviation and issue advisories about post-storm depressions within 96 hours after a geomagnetic storm accompanied by a K_p index of at least 6 (Kauristie et al., 2021). This paper aims to verify these two threshold values, the level of magnetic field disturbance and the time after the disturbance. To do this, we processed the arrays of depression maps accumulated in the databases of the Space Research Centre of the Polish Academy of Sciences (CBK PAN) since January 2020 (the service was launched in CBK PAN into operational work of PECASUS European space weather center in November 2019). It is worth noting that since 2024, ionosonde data from Akademik Vernadsky station has been implemented into the operational work of PECASUS through the servers of the Institute of Radio Astronomy NAS of Ukraine and CBK PAN.

We present the results of statistical analysis of the impact of geomagnetic storms on the occurrence of foF2 depression of more than 30% level. It is demonstrated that after the planetary K_p index equals 3, no changes in the probability of depression are observed. A slight increase in the probability foF2 is started from $K_p = 4$, and confidently registered for $K_p = 5$ and bigger. The time interval of growth in the probability of depression for $K_p = 4...7$ is about 36 hours. When $K_p = 8...9$, the time of impact increases significantly. The maximum reaction of foF2 depressions is observed at about 6–12 hours after the biggest K_p index of the storm. These results might be useful for optimizing the threshold criteria for issuing advisories about post-storm depressions in space weather centers. Additionally, we will discuss the global dynamics of post-storm depressions observed during and after the Mother’s Day geomagnetic storm of May 2024.

Kauristie, K., Andries, J., Beck, P., et al. (2021). Space Weather Services for Civil Aviation – Challenges and Solutions. *Remote Sensing*, 13, 18. <https://www.mdpi.com/2072-4292/13/18/3685>